

Inflation and Nigerian Investment Growth: Engle-Granger Two Step Modeling (EGM) Approach

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Abstract

This study makes a modest contribution to the debates by empirically analyzing the relationship between Nigeria inflation trend and investment growth (gross fixed capital formation), using time series data from 1980 to 2015, obtained from the World Economic Outlook (WEO) database of the IMF and World Development Indicators (World Data Bank Online Version). It employs the Engle-Granger two step modeling (EGM) procedure to co-integration based on unrestricted Error Correction Model and Pair wise Granger Causality tests. From the analysis, my findings indicate that inflation and gross fixed capital formation are cointegrated in this study. The error correction term of -0.76 is negatively signed and also significant at all conventional level indicating that when the variables wander away from equilibrium following an exogenous shock, 76 percent of the disequilibrium is corrected after one year. Based on the result of granger causality, the paper concludes that causality exist between the two variables used in this study. Therefore, the policy implication of these findings is that government should adopt various policy measures (both monetary and fiscal) to reduce inflation to an acceptable level because the current inflationary trend in Nigeria is negatively affecting the realization of creativity and manufacturing of commodities with international competitive advantage.

Keywords: Inflation, Gross Fixed Capital Formation, ECM, Growth

1 Introduction

According to Barro (1995) the relationship between inflation and economic growth is one of the most popular macroeconomic issues among central bankers, policy makers and macroeconomists. Investors are likely to hear the terms inflation and economic growth almost every day. They are often made to feel that these metrics must be studied as a nephrologist would study a patient's laboratory result before carrying out a dialysis or kidney transplant. The chances are that we have some concept of what they mean and how they interact, but what do we do when the best economic minds in the country can't agree on fundamental distinctions between how much the Nigerian economy should grow, or how much inflation is too much for the financial markets to handle? Individual investors need to find a level of understanding that assists their decision-making without inundating them in piles of data.

According to Mishkin (2001) as reported by Munyeka (2014) inflation is a rise in the general level of prices of goods and services in an economy over a period of time. When the general price level rises, each unit of currency buys fewer goods and services. Consequently, inflation also reflects erosion in the purchasing power of money a loss of real value in the internal medium of exchange and unit of account in the economy. An increase in inflation means that prices have risen. With an increase in inflation, there is a decline in the purchasing power of money, which reduces consumption and therefore GDP decreases. High inflation can make investments less desirable, since it creates uncertainty for the future and it can also affect the balance of payments because exports become more expensive. As a result, GDP is decreased further. So it appears that GDP is negatively related to inflation. However, there are studies indicating that there may also be a positive relationship. The Phillips curve, for example, shows that high inflation is consistent with low rates of unemployment, implying that there is a positive impact on economic growth.

The effect of inflation on investment occurs directly and indirectly. Inflation increases transactions and information costs, which directly inhibits economic development. For example, when inflation makes nominal

values uncertain, investment planning becomes difficult. Individuals may be reluctant to enter into contracts when inflation cannot be predicted making relative prices uncertain. This reluctance to enter into contracts over time will inhibit investment which will affect economic growth. In this case inflation will inhibit investment and could result in financial recession (Hellerstein, 1997). In an inflationary environment intermediaries will be less eager to provide long-term financing for capital formation and growth. Both lenders and borrowers will also be less willing to enter long-term contracts. High inflation is often associated with financial repression as governments take actions to protect certain sectors of the economy. For example, interest rate ceilings are common in high inflation environments. Such controls lead to inefficient allocations of capital that inhibit economic growth (Morley, 1971).

Sustained inflation is damaging to long-run growth and the financial system in general. Increases in inflation lead to lower real returns not just on money, but on all other assets too. These low returns interfere with the functioning of financial markets and the allocation of investment. Lower real returns have the effect of severely damaging the credit market. As a result, higher inflation contracts the supply of credit available to fund capital investment damaging the economy (Blume, 1978). It has been shown that inflation affects investment in several ways, mostly inhibiting economic growth. The source of inflation is money and the supply of it. Investors need to be able to expect returns in order for them to make financial decisions. If people cannot trust money then, they are less likely to engage in business relationships. This results in lower investment, production and less socially positive interactions. Among other effects, people may start to attempt to trade by other, less efficient, means in order to avoid the unpredictable price levels due to inflation.

Structuralists argue that inflation is crucial for economic growth, the monetarists posit that inflation is harmful to economic growth. The two basic aspects of the debate relate to the presence as well as nature of relationship between inflation and growth and the direction of causality. Commenting on the inconclusive nature of the relationship between inflation and economic growth, Friedman (1973) noted that some countries have experienced inflation with and without development and vice versa. Also, in a study on Nigeria, Chimobi (2010) investigates the existence of a relationship between inflation and economic growth using annual data for the period 1970 –2005. The study finds no co-integrating relationship between the two variables. Using Granger causality test, however, the study established unidirectional causality running from inflation to economic growth. Basically, the rate at which economic growth manifest depends primarily on the level of capital formation; and the degree of capital formation is a function of savings and investment rate. Therefore, whether inflation affects real output growth is a function of whether it affects the level of savings and investment both in the short and long-run, respectively (Olu & Idih, 2015).

According to Fatukasi (2012), in Nigeria, notwithstanding the several efforts directed by the government to curb inflation, these efforts have not yielded positive or desired results as high price level continued to cause setbacks in the growth rate of the living standard of the most Nigerians who are either on fixed income or are unemployed. He added that it has adverse effects on investment productivity, balance of payment and therefore reduced growth rate of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The inflation rate in Nigeria was highest in 1995 (72%) and lowest in 2007 (5.38) between 1980 and 2015. Inflation trend during the period of study show that the country witnessed single digit inflation rates in seven years (1980, 1982, 1985, 1986, 1990, 1997, 1999, 2000, 2006, 2007, 2013, 2014 and 2015) which is indicative of negative signals of Nigeria's investment environment (IMF, 2016) see figure 1.

In Nigeria's case, studies by Omoke (2010), to ascertain the existence (or not) of a relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria maintained the fact that the causality that run from inflation to economic growth is an indication of relationship showing that inflation indeed has a negative impact on growth. Aso (2004), in her work on the effect of inflation on the Nigerian economy" covering the period (1980-2002) found out that inflation has significantly affected Nigerian economy. Udabah (1998) who studied on evaluation

of the effectiveness of monetary policy in the Nigerian economy” covering the period (1995–1997) found out that the monetary policy instrument used by Central Bank contributed significantly in achieving some degree of macroeconomic stability. Iloabachie (2010) carried out a study on deficits and inflation in Nigeria, using the Granger–causality test, spanning from 1970–1994 confirmed that fiscal deficit causes inflation. He concluded that what should be of paramount concern to policy makers as regards inflation should not so much be the level of fiscal deficits, but the sources of its financing as well as the absorptive capacity of the economy. He recommended that policies to control inflation should have inbuilt ability to increase the productivity capacity of the economy.

Most of the papers are on the relationship between inflation and economic growth. This paper will examine several different economic theories and empirical studies to assess the effect of inflation on the growth of investment in Nigeria. Ultimately, the paper will test whether a meaningful relationship between the two variables exists in Nigeria. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 uses recent data to provide some stylized facts on Nigeria’s inflation-investment nexus. Section three reviews both the theoretical and empirical literature for the study. While section four discusses the methodology adapted for the study. Section five is for data analysis, discussion of results and conclusions.

Figure 1: Nigeria Inflation Trend (1980-2015)

Source: IMF, 2016

2 Investment Growth-Inflation Nexus in Nigeria: Some Stylized Facts

Investment growth in Nigerian during the period of study was 6.7 percent while the rate of inflation was 20 percent. This level of growth can be regarded as impressive going by the rate of inflation but if compared yearly, World Bank (2017) data on investment growth in Nigeria show that in 1981, Nigeria investment increased by 59.4 percent while inflation rate was 20 percent. This high growth rate could be attributed to the revenue from oil which stood at N10.366 billion between April and December 1980 (CBN, 2006). The rate of inflation reduced to 7.7 percent in 1982, investment growth decreased by -22.4 percent which can also be attributed to the revenue base of the country. By mid-1981, the oil glut returned in full-force and oil price experienced a dramatic tumbling down, that by 1983, it has tumbled to N18.00 per barrel. Nigeria's crude-oil OPEC quota which was some 2.3 million barrels per day in the 1970's, was reduced to about 1.3 million barrels per day in the early 1980's. This trend in the revenue base of the country also show that inflation rate was single digit for four years between 1980 and 1986. Investment growth remained negative between 1982 and 1987 except in 1984 (34 percent) when the military took over power. During this period, for every N1.00 of manufacturing output in Nigeria, at least 60 kobo was spent on imports on the average. No wonder then that the manufacturing sector collapsed with the disappearance of the oil boom.

Though there were heavy inflationary pressures 1993 (57.2 percent), investment growth increased by 16 percent. Inflation rate was highest during the period of study in 1995 (72 percent) and investment growth was negative (26.2 percent), that same year investment contribution to GDP fell from 11 percent in 1993 to 7 percent in 1995. Inflation rate fell from 17 percent in 2005 to 9 percent in 2015 while the growth of investment improved from -10.5 to 6 percent growth in 2015 see figure 2.

Investment contribution to the GDP during the period of study averaged 13.5%, it was highest in 1980 (43.4%) and lowest in 2005 (5.4%). Inflation rate decreased to a single digit of 7.7 percent in 1983 from a double digit of 20.8 and investment output decreased by 3.2 percent in 1983 this could also be attributed to the crisis going on in the economy as a result of the fall in the price of crude oil and OPEC's allocation quota to Nigeria. The trend of inflation doesn't really show a positive or negative relationship with investment output because most of the years the country recorded a single inflation rate it did not result to a significant growth in the output of investment except in 1989 when inflation rate fell from 50.5 to 7.4 in 1980, investment output increased by 17 percent which can be attributed to the relaxation of the second indigenization decree, the Nigerian Enterprise Promotion Decree of 1977, which tightened restrictions on FDI entry in 1989 see figure 3.

Figure 2: Inflation Trend and Investment Growth

Figure 3: Inflation Trend and Investment Output

3 Review of Related Literature

The relationship between inflation and economic growth have extensively been investigated in the economic literature. Most of this research work has been done internationally. This paper will critically review some of these important empirical studies to develop objectives in the context of Nigeria and, further, to analyze it to draw some important conclusions and policy recommendations.

3.1 Theoretical Review

Relationship between inflation and economic growth remains controversial in both theory and empirical findings. Theoretical models analyze the impact of inflation on growth focusing on the effects of inflation on the steady state investment and output. There are different possible results of the relationship between inflation and economic growth in these theoretical models. These are positive, neutral, negative or nonlinear relationship between the two variables. The first result is originally related with the work of Mundell (1963) and Tobin (1965) that concludes positive relationship between economic growth and inflation.

Mundell (1963) is the first to show that expected inflation has a real economic effect using the IS-LM curves. He argues that the money rate of interest rises by less than the rate of inflation and therefore that the real rate of interest falls during inflation. He assumes that real investment depends on the real interest rate and real saving on real balances and also inflation decreases real money balances. This creates decline in wealth which in turn stimulates increased saving. He claims that the advantages and disadvantages of inflation are not only due to the failure of the community to anticipate it. Expectation of fluctuations in the rate of inflation has real effects on economic activity. When prices are expected to increase, the money rate of interest rises by less than the rate of inflation giving impetus to an investment boom and an acceleration of growth and vice versa.

Tobin (1965) assumes money as a store value in the economy and shows that inflation has positive effect on economic growth. Money serves no useful role other than as a financial capital asset like physical capital. Tobin effect suggests that inflation causes individuals to acquire more capital than holding money because money and capital ratio depends negatively on the inflation rate, which leads to greater capital intensity and promotes economic growth. Tobin's framework shows that a higher inflation rate raises the level of output. However, the effect on output growth is temporary, occurring during the transition from one steady state capital stock to another steady state capital. Output and consumption therefore rise in the steady state. He also argues that, because of the downward rigidity of prices, the adjustment in relative prices during economic growth could be better achieved by the upward price movement of some individual prices.

Stockman (1981) developed cash in advance transactions constraint model which considers money as complimentary to capital. Stockman assumes that firms put up some cash in financing their consumption and investment goods. Real purchases of these goods decrease with decreased of money holding. He obtains that an increase in the inflation rate results in a lower steady state level of output, since inflation erodes the purchasing power of money balances; people reduce their holding of cash and purchase of capital when the inflation rate rises. Correspondingly, the steady-state level of output falls in response to an increase in the inflation rate. This is the other possible result of the relation between inflation and economic growth in theoretical models.

Manuelli and Jones (1995) consider models of endogenous growth with formulation of supply of effective labor to show the effect of money growth on welfare and economic growth. They assume that demand for money is generated for transaction purpose. If nominal depreciation is included in the tax code, real marginal tax rate on investment income is altered by inflation rate. As inflation rate rises, the discounted value of depreciation tax credits decreases, and therefore the effective tax on capital income gets higher. People slow their rate of capital accumulation due lower after tax return on capital. This decreases the rate of economic growth.

In general, from the theoretical models discussed above, it is clear that the results depend on the assumption about the economy identified and also depend on the set up of the models. All the models try to make their conclusion in line with economic theories. Accordingly, inflation may have positive, negative, neutral or nonlinear relationship on economic growth in these theoretical models.

3.2 Empirical Review

Up until the mid of 1970s there was little empirical evidence for any relationship between inflation and economic growth and even there were doubts in which direction the relationship should be. Like the theoretical models, results of empirical studies change through time from the widely known traditional point of view of positive relationship between inflation and economic growth to nonlinear relationship in recent years. Now many economists are convinced that low but positive inflation is good for the betterment of a given economy.

The traditional point of view does not consider inflation as an important factor in growth equation. Barro (1996) analyses the effect of inflation and other variables like fertility, democracy and others on economic growth in different countries for a period of 30 years. He uses system of regression equation in which other determinants of growth are held constant. To estimate the effect inflation on economic growth without looking at the

endogeneity problem of inflation, he includes inflation as explanatory variable over each period along with other determinants of economic growth. The result indicates that there is a negative relationship between inflation and growth with a coefficient of -0.024. One problem arising from the above conclusion is that the regression may not show causation from inflation to growth. Inflation is an endogenous variable that may respond to growth and other variables related to growth. For example an inverse relationship between inflation and growth may arise if an exogenous falling down of growth rate tended to generate higher inflation rate. He uses instrumental variables like independence of the central bank, lagged inflation and prior colonial status, each these variables are related to inflation, to avoid this problem. The result is statistically significant and strengthens the negative relationship between the inflation and growth. Thus, there is some reason to believe that the relation reflect causation from higher long term inflation to reduced growth. Finally, he concludes that even though the results looks small, the long-term effects on standards of living can be substantial.

Fischer (1993) showed that inflation and growth are negatively related. More specifically, he argues that growth, investments and productivity are negatively related to inflation and that capital accumulation and productivity growth are also negatively affected by budget deficits. Moreover, he states that some exceptional cases show that even though high growth is not necessarily associated with low inflation and small budget deficits, high rates of inflation are not consistent with permanent growth. Gillman and Nakov (2003) studies effects of inflation within an endogenous growth monetary economy. The result shows that accelerating inflation raises the ratio of the real wage to the real interest rate, and so raises the use of physical capital relative to human capital across all sectors. Their result is consistent with a general equilibrium, Tobin-type, effect of inflation on input prices and capital intensity.

Nevertheless, the traditional point of view changed when high and chronic inflation was present in many countries in the 1970s. As a result, different researchers showed that inflation has a negative impact on output growth. Ghosh and Phillips (1998) studied the relationship between inflation and GDP for a large set of IMF countries for the period from 1960 to 1996. They found that, generally, the coefficient, with respect to inflation, was negative. The findings were statistically significant. More specifically, they found two nonlinearities in the inflation– growth relationship. The relationship between these appeared to be negative for very low inflation rates (around two to three per cent). They also found a negative correlation for higher values but the relationship was convex, meaning that a decline in growth related to an increase of from ten to 20 per cent inflation was larger than that related to an increase in inflation of from 40 to 50 per cent.

Andres and Hernando (1997) obtain a significant negative relationship between inflation and economic growth during long periods. Inflation reduces the level of investment as well as the efficiency with which factors of are used. It has a negative temporary impact on long term growth rates, which in turn generates permanent fall in per capita income. They conclude that the long run cost of inflation is large and the effort to keep inflation down will pay off in terms of better economic growth.

Omoke (2010) in his study tried ascertain the existence (or not) of a relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria employing the cointegration and Granger Causality test. Consumer price index (CPI) was used as a proxy for inflation and the GDP as a perfect proxy for economic growth to examine the relationship. The result of the test showed that for the periods, 1970-2005, there was no cointegrating relationship between inflation and economic growth for Nigeria data. The results showed the same at different lags. Unidirectional causality was seen running from inflation to economic growth showing that inflation indeed has an impact on growth.

The foregoing review reveals that there is a nexus between inflation and economic growth. Therefore, the impact of inflation on investment growth of Nigeria is the target of this study.

4 Methodology

4.1 Scope of study

This study was designed to cover a period of 36 years (1980- 2015). A time series data was used for this study. Data used in this study were obtained from the World Economic Outlook (WEO) database of the IMF. The database contains selected macroeconomic data series from the statistical appendix of the World Economic Outlook report, which presents the IMF staff's analysis and projections of economic developments at the global level, in major country groups and in many individual countries and World Development Indicators (World Data Bank Online Version).

4.2 Description of Time Series Variables Used

1. Inflation Rate (INF_t): This is the percentage change in the general price level of goods and services in Nigeria from 1980- 2015.
2. Gross Fixed Capital Formation: It refers to net additions of capital stock such as equipment, buildings and other intermediate goods. A nation uses capital stock in combination with labour to provide services and produce goods; an increase in this capital stock is known as capital formation. Generally, the higher the capital formation of an economy, the faster an economy can grow its aggregate income. Increasing an economy's capital stock also increases its capacity for production, which means an economy can produce more. Producing more goods and services can lead to an increase in national income levels.

4.3 Model Specification

Engle-Granger two step modeling (EGM) procedure (Engle and Granger, 1987) has been widely used to test for long-run relationship. If X_t and Y_t are individually $I(1)$ processes and there exist a linear combination of this variables that is $I(0)$ process, then X_t and Y_t are cointegrated. In other words, a long run equilibrium relationship exists among these variables. Based on the Granger Representation Theorem (GRT), if two variables are cointegrated, there exists an Error Correction Model (ECM) which relates these variables in the short-run while maintaining the consistency of the OLS estimated long-run parameter obtained in the cointegrating regression. In this instance, ECM indicates the periodic change in the time series variables and how it eventually returns to its long run equilibrium value. Since the ECM equation contains only stationary variables which preclude spurious regression, granger causality test can be applied. This is because cointegration analysis shows that there is causality amongst variables but it does not reveal the direction of such causality.

The long-run cointegrating regression is given as follows

$$LGFCF_t = \phi INF_t + u_t \quad (1)$$

Where LGFCF represents the natural log of gross fixed capital formation and INF represents inflation. $LGFCF_t$ and INF_t are both nonstationary variables and integrated of order one (i.e. $LGFCF_t \sim I(1)$ and $INF_t \sim I(1)$). The necessary condition for cointegration is that the estimated residual from equation (1) be stationary (i.e. $U_t \sim I(0)$). If the above conditions are met, ECM is estimated from this model.

$$\Delta LGFCF_t = \delta_1 \Delta INF_t + \delta_2 \theta_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where Δ is the first difference operator, ε_t is the error term and θ is the estimated residual from equation (1) (i.e. $LGFCF_t - \phi INF_t$). GRT requires that the coefficient δ_2 in the short-run equation (2) be negative and statistically significant to confirm the cointegration of the variables. Note that the estimation of the ECM precludes the question of spurious regression since the variables are stationary and equally incorporates both the static long-run and dynamic short-run components.

Granger causality analysis is used to test the hypothesis of prediction of future values of a particular variable(s) while incorporating the past lags of other variables in the model. In other words, a time series variable X_t is said to granger cause another time series variables Y_t if the former contains useful information to predict future values of the later. In this framework, if the F-test of the included lagged variables is statistically significantly

different from zero, it implies that there is causality which can either be unidirectional or bidirectional in a bivariate case.

The granger causality test is estimated from the following equations

$$\Delta LGFCF_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \Delta LGFCF_{t-j} + u_{1t} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta INF_t = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_j \Delta LGFCF_{t-j} + u_{2t} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where α, β, λ and γ are the respective coefficient of the variables, t represents time while i and j are their lags, u_{1t} and u_{2t} are uncorrelated white noise error term. The null hypothesis is $\alpha = 0$ for all i_s and $\gamma = 0$ for all j_s while the alternative hypothesis is given as $\alpha_i \neq 0$ and $\gamma_j \neq 0$.

4.4 Results

The study will begin by exploring the time series properties of the variables. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (1979) test and (PP) Phillips and Perron (1988) test for unit root is deployed to test the stationarity of the variables. The ADF tests the null hypothesis of nonstationarity while the confirmatory PP test for stationarity of the null hypothesis. Table 1 reports the result of the ADF and PP test for both the levels and first-difference of the variable.

Table 1. ADF and KPSS Unit Root Test for LGFCF and INF

Variable	ADF test		PP	
	level	First Difference	level	First Difference
LGFCF	0.302669	-10.85896	0.306971	-10.28948
INF	-0.078292	-4.499237	-0.111798	-4.499237
5% Critical Value	-2.933	-2.935	-2.933	-2.935

Note the ADF 5% critical value for constant and trend is 3.568379

Table 1 reveals that both variables are nonstationary at level but are stationary at their first-difference. In short, both variables are integrated of order one (i.e. they are $I(1)$ processes) which sets the stage for cointegration test. Below is the estimated result of the cointegrating equation (1).

$$LGFCF_t = 5.72 - 0.79 INF_t$$

(0.25) (0.09)

Note that the standard error is given in parenthesis below the estimated coefficient. The coefficient of INF is statistically significant different from zero. From this estimation, we retrieved the residual and performed ADF test and confirm that it is integrated of order zero. (i.e $U_t \sim I(0)$) (Result is not reported to save space) and used it to estimate the ECM of equation (2). The result is given below

$$\Delta LGFCF_t = -0.11 + 1.07 \Delta INF_t - 0.76 \theta_{t-1}$$

(0.17) (0.00) (0.00)

$$R^2 = 0.67 \quad d = 1.5$$

The estimated coefficient of the ECM term which is also the speed of adjustment to equilibrium is negative and statistically significant as required by the granger representation theorem. This is enough evidence that GFCF and INF are cointegrated in this study. The speed of adjustment to equilibrium is 76% within a year when the variables wander away from their equilibrium values.

Table 2. Pair wise Granger causality test

Direction of causality	F-stat	pvalue	Decision	Lag length
GFCF → INF	2.73	0.06*	Do not reject	2
GFCF ← INF	0.54	0.66	Reject	2

The arrow shows the direction of causality.

In many previous studies which examine causality, Granger Causality tests have been the most commonly used method. This is because it not only tests the correlation between two variables (as is tested by traditional approaches such as OLS regression), but also specifies the direction of causality. However, growth and inflation, as widely suggested by many economist scholars in the literature reviewed are known to relate inversely, in other words, the economy does not grow well in the midst of high inflation. In any case the following result shown in the table 2 above, reveals the direction of causality between investment growth and inflation at lag three (3). First a VAR model is fitted to the time series data in order to find an appropriate lag structure. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion (SC) and the Likelihood Ratio (LR) test are used to select the number of lags required with author's estimation using Eviews 9.

The hypothesis that inflation and investment growth in Nigeria are statistically significantly different from zero is not rejected for the third lag length as the p-values of the F-test indicate. Based on the result of granger causality, we conclude that causality exist between the two variables used in this study which is in line with economic theory.

5 Conclusion

In this study, we set out to empirically investigate the empirical relationship between the rate of inflation and investment growth (gross fixed capital formation), using annual time series data from 1980 to 2015. Some econometric tools are employed to explore the relationship between these variables. The study examines stochastic characteristics of each time series by testing their stationarity using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test. Then, the relationship between inflation, and investment growth (gross fixed capital formation) is examined using Engle-Granger two step modeling (EGM) procedure and Pairwise Granger causality tests. The results from the Test indicate that there exists a relationship between inflation, and investment growth (gross fixed capital formation) in the short and long-run. In addition, the causality results reveal that at all conventional level of significance and at three lag lengths, a unidirectional causality running from investment growth to inflation with no reverse causality (no feedback) from inflation to investment growth. According to empirical findings of this study, one may tentatively suggest that high inflation affects investment growth in Nigeria negatively as indicated in the short and long run period. Similarly, inflation rate can be predicted with great accuracy by using past values of investment growth, all other thing remaining unchanged or held constant.

The study recommends that Monetary authority should create and implement monetary policies that favour efficient provision of more investment climate by facilitating the emergency of market based interest rate and exchange rate regimes that attract both domestic and foreign investment in the long run. The Central Bank should make more stringent punishment for non-compliance to the monetary policies by financial institutions most especially in the provision of credit facility for investment in the country.

Low or moderate inflation is an indicator of macroeconomic stability and creates an environment conducive for investment. Countries with low or moderate rates of inflation have higher growth rates over the long-term compared with countries with high inflation rates. However, low inflation does not constitute a sufficient condition for growth. To promote growth and keep inflation low, the government needs to control budget deficits. This can be achieved by switching public expenditure from consumption to investment, this may be a difficult policy to pursue, especially in a developing country with a multiparty democracy. It may be more realistic to choose 'tolerable' levels of inflation rate and achieve the maximum possible growth given that rate, by deficit-financed public investment.

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